

Abstract of the presentation

Title: Southeast Mexico: Poor Development in the Richest Region

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Institution: University of Sussex

Program: MSc Sustainable Development

Area of the presentation: Social Sciences and Humanities & Public Policies

A bill establishing three Special Economic Zones (ZEE) in the center and south of the country was published in September 2017. The ZEE aim to detonate regional development through flexible and attractive conditions for investments, such as discounts in tax payments and benefits for companies that train their employees, among others. The presentation focuses on the case of Campeche, one of the chosen locations.

This state in Southeast Mexico has one of the largest stocks of natural resources in the whole country, including oil, forestry, and fishing, among others. However, even though this has been widely exploited in the past, Campeche has severely underperformed in the past 10 years, having spent almost the totality of the period in an economic recession.

This presentation aims to contribute to the analysis of the Special Economic Zones program, asking whether a development strategy based on the exploitation of natural resources, as implied by the election of the zones and the investment proposals received until now, may generate sustainable relationships in three dimensions: social, economic and environmental. The presentation proposes to identify key factors behind the Southeast failure and open the doors to new paradigms that contribute to the generation of inclusive development strategies in our country.